

THE DELAMINATION GROWTH IN FMLS UNDER FATIGUE LOAD BASED ON DIC METHOD

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ABSTRACT

Glass fiber reinforced aluminum alloy laminates (FMLs) is a new kind of composite material, which has more excellent specific strength, specific stiffness, anti-fatigue and impact resistance. Delamination is the main damage of FMLs. This paper designed several samples with different notch sizes and performed the delamination growth under different fatigue loads. Based on DIC method, the shapes and sizes of delamination and crack lengths were calculated. It is shown that delamination growth slows down along the loading direction with crack growing. The crack growth rates decrease firstly, then remain almost stable for a long crack growth, and rise rapidly at last. The effects of stress ratios and notch sizes on delamination growth and crack propagation were analyzed.

1 INTRODUCTION

By using FMLs in aircraft components can meet the technical requirements of long life, high reliability and light weight [1]. The exceptional properties of FMLs have been proven by successfully applying in A380 [2]. Digital Image Correlation (DIC) is a new technology that can directly provide full-field displacements to sub-pixel accuracy and full-field strains by comparing the digital images of a test object surface acquired before and after deformation, which has the advantages of convenience, high-accuracy, low cost and broad prospects [3]. The objective of this research is to study the mode of delamination growth and the effects of stress ratios and notch sizes in FMLs under fatigue load using DIC method.

2 SAMPLE DESIGN AND EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

Fibre-metal laminates (FMLs) is a kind of hybrid material which consists of alternating layers of thin metallic sheets bonded together with fibre reinforced layers. Glass fiber reinforced aluminum alloy plates (FMLs) is made by alternating layers of 2024-T3 and S2-glass fibre. All layers are [Al/0°/90°/0°/Al/0°/90°/0°/Al], and 0° is along rolling direction of aluminum. Middle crack tension sample (M(T) sample) is used according to ASTM E647. Test sample is 700×140×1.662 mm typical specimens that were made up with S2-glass fiber and 2024-T3 aluminum alloy, where the thickness of aluminum layer is 0.254mm and that of fiber is 0.15 mm. Two different notches (10 mm and 20 mm) are made in the middle of samples. The size of sample is shown in Fig.1.

Figure 1: Size of sample

The delamination growth of FMLs with different notch under different fatigue loads was tested and the crack length and delamination shapes were obtained by Aramis [4-6]. In order to study fatigue response of FMLs, the notch $2a=10/20\text{mm}$ and the two types of fatigue load were set up : (1) 160MPa , $R=0.1$ and (2) 180MPa , $R=0.2$ separately. Here, we set FML 10-1 as the specimen with $2a=10\text{mm}$ and the load type 1; Similarly, FML 20-2 represents the specimen with $2a=20\text{mm}$ and the load type 2. The load condition and test results were shown in Table 1.

Figure 2: DIC method preparations

Figure 3: Testing set up

Table 1 Load condition

Sample	Pre-crack (mm)	Load			
		σ (MPa)	P_{\max} (KN)	R	f(Hz)
FML 10-1	10	160	37.6	0.1	10
FML 10-2	10	180	42.3	0.2	10
FML 20-1	20	160	37.6	0.1	10
FML 20-2	20	180	42.3	0.2	10

3. RESULTS

3.1 Experimental Results

Software Aramis is used to calculate strain change during the crack growing. The strain change along load direction at 0 , 15×10^4 , 26×10^4 and 34×10^4 cycle is shown in Figure 4. The red color means the main crack length, and the blue color is the delamination shape. The development of crack and delamination growing can be clearly seen.

Figure 4: Strain of FML 20-1 by DIC method

Figure 5 (a) and (b) shows delamination length of FML10-1 and FML10-2 at 34×10^4 cycle and 17×10^4 cycle when the crack length is 26 mm long. Delamination area of FML10-2 is smaller one of FML 10-1. This is because fatigue R ratio of FML 10-2 is 0.2 while fatigue R ratio of FML 10-1 is 0.1. If the R ratio is bigger, crack growing dominates damage mode of FMLs. Figure 5 (c) and (d) shows delamination length of FML20-1 and FML10-1 at 20×10^4 cycle and 50×10^4 cycle when the crack length is 32 mm long. Delamination area of FML10-1 is smaller one of FML 20-1. If fatigue load and R ratio keep the same, the sample with smaller notch has the smaller delamination area when the crack grows and reaches the same length. Figure 5 (e) and (f) shows delamination length of FML20-1 and FML20-2 at 31×10^4 cycle and 20×10^4 cycle when the crack length is 45 mm long. Delamination area of FML10-2 is smaller one of FML 20-1. This is because fatigue R ratio of FML 20-2 is 0.2 while fatigue R ratio of FML 20-1 is 0.1.

Figure 5: The delamination comparison at different crack length by DIC method

It is shown that the delamination area is related to the stress ratio and the pre-crack length. The delamination area is larger for the specimen with smaller stress ratio and that with longer pre-crack. Fatigue crack propagation lives of all samples are obtained and shown in Table 2.

Table 2 Fatigue crack propagation life

Sample	Fatigue life (N)	Photo number
FML 10-1	500000	51
FML 10-2	228380	23
FML 20-1	345495	35
FML 20-2	214671	22

Fatigue life crack growth rates are compared and shown in Figure 6. Figure 6 (a) shows crack growth rates of sample FMLs 20 with the same notch length. When cracks start to propagate, crack growth rates decrease a little and then keep constant value to grow. Before crack length is 35 mm, crack growth rate of FML20-2 is a little bit higher than one of FML 20-1. After crack length is longer than 35mm, fibres of sample FML20-2 began to fracture firstly, and then bridge stress effect of fibre becomes weak. So crack of FML20-2 accelerate to grow under fatigue R=0.2 ratio load. Figure 6(b) shows crack growth rates of FML20-2 and FML10-2. It is shown that the sample with shorter notch has smaller crack growth rate under the same load.

For the crack growth rate, it firstly descended, then leveled off and accelerated finally. A bigger stress ratio and a longer notch both can speed up the crack propagation rate.

In order to study the relation between delamination length and crack length, the ratio of delamination length versus crack length was calculated and compared in Figure 7. With crack propagating, the ratio of delamination length versus crack length become smaller, and it will try to keep at about 0.42 after crack length is longer than 20.0 mm.

Figure 6: Crack propagation rates

Figure 7: Ratio of Delamination length and crack length versus crack length

3. 2 Comparison of calculation and experimental results

According to Ref. [7-11], programs were made to calculate bridge stress of fibre and its change with crack growing. We can obtain delamination length of FML20-1 at 12×10^4 , 17×10^4 , 26×10^4 and 30×10^4 cycle and compare with experimental results shown in Figure 8. In Figure 8, the line is the calculation results. The calculated delamination length grew big with fatigue cycle increasing and it is smaller than the experimental one. Bridge stress effect is taken into consider in calculation equations, but it is complex during testing process.

(a) 12×10^4 cycle

(b) 17×10^4 cycle

Figure8: Calculation and experimental results of delamination length

4. CONCLUSIONS

- (1) DIC method can be used to capture delamination growing;
- (2) Delamination length can be related to fatigue load and notch size;
- (3) Delamination will decrease when crack length is longer than 20 mm;
- (4) A big stress ratio can enlarge the crack propagation but reduce the delamination area.
- (5) Delamination can be calculated based on bridge stress theory.

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